

doi:10.5281/zenodo.19256169

Family Relationship Patterns As Correlates Of Maladaptive Behaviour Of Public Senior Secondary School Students In Rivers State

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ABSTRACT

The study investigated family relationship patterns as correlates of maladaptive behaviour of public senior secondary school students in Rivers State. The study adopted a correlational research design. Three research questions and three hypotheses were formulated to guide the study. The population of the study comprised the entire public senior secondary school two (SS2) students in Rivers State numbering 10,120 (Rivers State Post Primary Schools Board, 2025). A sample size of 417 public senior secondary school students was drawn from the population using the simple random sampling technique. The instrument for data collection was a researcher developed instrument titled: "Family Relationship Patterns and Maladaptive Behaviour Scale" (FRPMBS). The face and content validities of the instrument were determined by two other experts in Guidance and Counselling Department of Rivers State University, Port Harcourt. The internal consistency method was used to determine the reliability of the instrument as $\alpha=.87$ for (FSRPS) and $\alpha=.70$ for (MBS). The research questions and hypotheses were answered and tested using Pearson's product moment correlation. All data were subjected to analysis using the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS). The result of the study revealed that neglectful parenting and parental conflict have significant strong positive relationship with maladaptive behaviour of public secondary school students in Rivers State. Authoritarian parenting has a significant weak positive relationship with maladaptive behaviour of public senior secondary school students in Rivers State. Based on the findings of the study, the researcher recommended among other things that: Authoritarian parents should adopt a more supportive and communicative approach by explaining the reasons behind family rules; this can help reduce maladaptive behaviour and promote adolescents' emotional and social development, in line with the goals of Sustainable Development Goal 4, which advocates supportive environments for quality education and positive youth development.

Keywords: Family, Relationships Patterns, Maladaptive Behaviours, Public Senior Secondary Students.

INTRODUCTION

Maladaptive behaviour is the generic name for the entirety of the unproductive, counterproductive or destructive overt or covert responses of individuals to environmental stimuli. It subsumes actions, responses, or patterns of thinking that interfere with an individual's ability to adjust to particular situations or achieve personal, social, or academic goals. Maladaptive behaviours are often detrimental in the long run and tend to hinder an individual's ability to cope with stress, relationships, work, or everyday challenges. They are typically categorized as behaviours manifested by an individual that are

counterproductive, dysfunctional, and often lead to negative outcomes for the individual or those around him or her (Iwundu, 2023).

In this view, the term maladaptive behaviour refers to any strategy, style or means of coping that is unhealthy or unethical and as such unproductive or counterproductive. Sanvictores and Mendez (2023) elucidated that maladaptive behaviour refers to actions or attitudes that hinder an individual's ability to adapt to his/her environment, leading to inadequate or harmful adjustment mechanisms; such behaviours that can interfere with social relationships, work, or daily functioning, and may even put the individual or others at risk.

The prevalent maladaptive behaviours observed among the public senior secondary school students in Rivers State that necessitated this study include; substance abuse, aggressive or violent behaviour, self-harm or suicidal tendencies, avoidance or escapist behaviours (e.g., truancy, absenteeism), dissociation or disconnection from others, compulsive or addictive behaviours (e.g., gambling, internet addiction), self-destructive or risky behaviours (e.g., reckless driving, compulsive buying, unsafe sex), enabling or codependent behaviours in relationships, passive-aggressive or manipulative behaviours and avoidance of responsibilities or obligation. Behaviours of this nature as posited by Iwundu (2019) are not only deleterious to students but also disastrous to members of the general public.

Gross and Munoz (2017) disclosed that maladaptive behaviours often stem from emotional regulation difficulties. It is worthy of note that emotional dysregulation can result in extreme reactions to stress, leading to behaviors like aggression, withdrawal, or self-destructive actions. Such behaviors are typically learned in childhood but can persist into adulthood if not addressed. Concomitantly, maladaptive behaviors are sometimes driven by cognitive distortions irrational or biased ways of thinking that influence an individual's behavior. For instance, a person may engage in catastrophizing (expecting the worst possible outcome) or overgeneralization (drawing broad conclusions from a single incident), leading to avoidance behaviors or extreme responses (Younesian, 2021).

It is pertinent to note that people who develop maladaptive behaviours often have ineffective coping strategies when facing stress or conflict. Rather than adapting to the environment, they may resort to avoidance, denial, or aggression, which further exacerbates the problem. These responses may provide short-term relief but are ultimately maladaptive in the long run. Iwundu (2020) informed that environmental factors such as familial dysfunction, peer pressure, or trauma can contribute to the development of maladaptive behaviors. A person raised in an environment where unhealthy coping strategies are modeled might learn to adopt similar responses to stress or difficulty and vice versa.

Be that as it may, it is worthy of note that maladaptive behaviour is usually marked by; avoidance, aggression, addictive behaviours, self-harm and social withdrawal (Younesian, 2021). The consequences of maladaptive behaviour therefore are wide-ranged and can impact various domains of life, including physical health, relationships, employment, and mental well-being. Individuals who engage in maladaptive behaviors may therefore experience: mental health disorders such as anxiety, depression, and personality disorders. And these behaviors can exacerbate the symptoms of these disorders, creating a vicious cycle (Iwundu & Andah, 2018).

Gross and Munoz (2017) advanced that maladaptive behaviors like aggression or withdrawal can significantly impair an individual's relationships with family, friends, and colleagues. These behaviors make it difficult for individuals to form healthy, lasting connections. Ultimately, maladaptive behaviors limit an individual's ability to thrive, both socially and professionally. They can lead to a lack of fulfillment, dissatisfaction with life, and a general sense of stagnation (Iwundu, 2020).

McKinney, Gose and Kline (2017) disclosed that the relationships between students, their families, and their schools play a significant role in shaping their behavior, particularly in terms of maladaptive behaviors. The family is one of the most influential environments in a child's life. It is the basic, structural and functional unit of socialization. Early interactions and experiences within the family as posited by Iwundu (2020) can shape a child's behavior patterns and emotional responses. Some family-related factors that can contribute to the development of maladaptive behaviors in students as envisaged by the researcher include: authoritarian parenting, neglectful parenting and parental conflict.

Authoritarian parents are rigid, controlling and demanding, often leading to rebellious or aggressive behaviors in children (Obiyo, Aye, Onuigbo & Ihebuzoaju, 2019). Children raised by authoritarian parents may have difficulty managing stress or frustration and may exhibit maladaptive behaviors, such as defiance or impulsivity given the conformance pressure placed on them by their parents.

Emami, Moghadasin and Mastour (2024) informed that neglectful parents tend to relegate or abscond from their parental duties, responsibilities or obligations. They more often than not fail to provide adequate emotional support or supervision for their children. Thus, children raised by neglectful parents may struggle with emotional regulation and social interactions. These children often exhibit withdrawal or disengagement in school, which can contribute to poor academic performance and a lack of social integration.

Ciuhan (2021) disclosed that high levels of parental conflict and allied stress, bordering on divorce, financial instability, or substance abuse, can contribute to maladaptive behaviors in children. Chronic stress within the family often leads to anxiety, depression, and behavioral problems, as children may not have the tools to process their emotions or regulate their responses. The stress and negative emotional atmosphere at home can spill over into school, resulting in difficulties with concentration, disruptive behavior, or a lack of engagement (Iwundu, 2020).

Lien, Rosen, Bloemen and Pavlour (2017) observed that children often learn behaviors by observing and imitating their parents or primary caregivers. If parents exhibit maladaptive behaviors like aggression, substance abuse, or emotional dysregulation, children may model these behaviors in their own interactions. This can result in poor coping mechanisms, difficulties in emotional regulation, and increased vulnerability to peer pressure or social isolation.

Luyckx et al. (2011) conducted a comprehensive 12-year longitudinal study to explore how variations in parenting practices contribute to the developmental trajectories of maladaptive behaviors in children and adolescents. Utilizing a cohort-sequential community sample of 1,049 children, the researchers employed latent class growth analysis (LCGA) to examine three core dimensions of parenting monitoring, positive parenting, and inconsistent discipline across 12 annual assessments from ages 6 to 18. Based on the patterns and rates of change across these dimensions, four longitudinally defined parenting styles emerged: authoritative, authoritarian, indulgent, and uninvolved. Multi-group analyses indicated that these parenting typologies were significantly associated with changes in various child behavioral outcomes, including alcohol and cigarette use, antisocial conduct, and internalizing symptoms, as reported by both parents and children. The authoritative parenting style, characterized by high monitoring and positive engagement coupled with low inconsistency, was consistently linked to the most favorable developmental outcomes while authoritarian parenting style was significantly linked to maladaptive behaviour. These findings underscore the long-term influence of parenting practices on child behavior and highlight the critical need for early intervention and parent-focused education to foster healthier developmental pathways. The reviewed study is related to the present study in terms of variables of interest they however differ with regard to area, population, instrumentation and analytical approach.

Emami et al. (2024) examined the combined influence of early maladaptive schemas (EMS), attachment styles (AS), and parenting styles (PS) on the development of personality disorders (PDs). The study sought to distinguish individuals with PDs from those without, by identifying specific psychological and relational variables that serve as discriminants. A sample of 78 individuals diagnosed with personality disorders and 360 psychologically healthy adults, aged between 18 and 84, participated in the research. Standardized instruments were employed, including the Schema Questionnaire-Short Form (SQ-SF), Revised Adult Attachment Scale (RAAS), and Baumrinds Parenting Styles Inventory (PSI). Through discriminant function analysis, the study found that individuals with PDs scored significantly higher across all EMS domains and were more likely to report insecure attachment patterns and authoritarian parenting styles. The statistical model effectively distinguished between clinical and non-clinical participants, with schemas related to disconnection, impaired autonomy, and attachment security emerging as particularly salient discriminators. These results suggest that interventions aimed at modifying maladaptive cognitive frameworks and early relational experiences may be effective in

mitigating the onset or severity of personality disorders. The reviewed study is related to the present study in terms of variables of interest they however differ with regard to area, population, instrumentation and analytical approach.

Bedu-Addo et al. (2023) conducted an empirical investigation into the predictive roles of neglectful parenting and personality traits in fostering malevolent creativity among university students in Ghana. Recognizing that human creativity can manifest in both constructive and destructive ways, the study explored how adverse environmental and personality-related factors influence the emergence of creativity with harmful intent referred to as malevolent creativity. Utilizing a cross-sectional research design, data were collected from a sample of 623 tertiary education students through standardized instruments measuring neglectful parenting experiences, personality dimensions, and malevolent creative behaviors. Structural equation modeling (CB-SEM) was employed to analyze the data. The findings revealed that both physical and emotional neglect significantly predicted higher levels of malevolent creativity, specifically in behaviors such as deceitfulness, manipulation, and intent to harm others. Interestingly, individuals scoring high in conscientiousness, typically associated with discipline and responsibility, also exhibited elevated levels of these harmful creative behaviors, suggesting a complex relationship between seemingly adaptive traits and antisocial tendencies. The authors concluded that neglectful and inconsistent parenting could contribute to the development of socially detrimental behaviors, urging communities to implement preventive strategies aimed at fostering healthier family dynamics and mitigating maladaptive personality development. The reviewed study is related to the present study in terms of variables of interest they however differ with regard to area, population, instrumentation and analytical approach.

Berzenski, Bennett, Marini Sullivan and Lewis (2013) examined the moderating influence of parental distress on the relationship between child neglect and psychological maladjustment, with particular attention to the differentiation between internalizing and externalizing behavioural issues. Drawing from a sample of 66 children, including 33 with confirmed cases of early childhood neglect reported by child protective services, the study assessed their emotional and behavioral functioning at age seven based on teacher evaluations. The results confirmed that childhood neglect was a strong predictor of internalizing symptoms such as anxiety and withdrawal, and to a lesser degree, externalizing behaviors like aggression. Notably, parental distress was found to moderate the relationship between neglect and internalizing problems, indicating that children of distressed parents were more susceptible to internal psychological difficulties following neglect. This research underscores the importance of parental emotional health as a contextual factor in the developmental outcomes of neglected children and suggests that interventions must address not only child-level variables but also parent-specific stress and coping capacities. The reviewed study is related to the present study in terms of variables of interest they however differ with regard to area, population, instrumentation and analytical approach.

Saijad et al. (2017) conducted a comprehensive inquiry into the influences of parental conflict on child behavior, emphasizing not only the traditionally examined negative outcomes but also potential constructive effects. While a substantial body of research has underscored the detrimental consequences of parental disputes on children's emotional and behavioral development, this study sought to explore a broader spectrum acknowledging that the impact of such conflict may range from significantly harmful to, in some cases, beneficial. The authors argued that repeated exposure to parental discord can disrupt a child's psychological stability and social behavior, leading to internalized emotional struggles such as distress, anxiety, or social withdrawal. However, they also suggest that, depending on the nature and resolution of the conflict, some children might develop resilience or enhanced social competencies. The study underscores the need for a nuanced and integrative understanding of how children emotionally interpret and respond to parental conflict, stressing that child behavior must be examined through both adaptive and maladaptive lenses in response to familial stress dynamics. The reviewed study is related to the present study in terms of variables of interest they however differ with regard to area, population, instrumentation and analytical approach.

Kong, Chen and Meng (2024) examined the mechanisms through which parental conflict contributes to adolescents socially adverse emotions, specifically focusing on shyness and loneliness, and explored the mediating role of family functioning. The study surveyed 1,100 junior high school students in urban China using stratified cluster sampling, providing insights into how family dynamics shape adolescent emotional development. Findings revealed that boys reported higher levels of shyness and loneliness compared to girls, and students in the second year of junior high school experienced more intense adverse emotions than those in the first year. Parental conflict was found to have a negative correlation with family functioning and a positive correlation with shyness and loneliness. Notably, family functioning partially mediated the relationship between parental conflict and shyness, and fully mediated the link between parental conflict and loneliness. The results suggest that a well-functioning family environment can buffer the harmful emotional outcomes of parental conflict, with a particularly strong protective effect against adolescent loneliness. This highlights the central role of family cohesion and adaptability in safeguarding youth emotional well-being. The reviewed study is related to the present study in terms of variables of interest they however differ with regard to area, population, instrumentation and analytical approach.

Until now, little or no studies have been conducted on family relationship pattern as correlates of maladaptive behaviour of public senior secondary school students in Rivers State. It is against this background that the researcher conducted the study.

Statement of the Problem

Nowadays lots of public senior secondary school students in Rivers State make frantic efforts to cope scholastically without recording much progress. It is perplexing to note that the students in question are taught and trained to develop requisite and exquisite knowledge, skills and values to make them become worthy in character and in learning. However, a whole lot of them tend to go haywire courtesy of their adjustment problems. It is not uncommon to see the affected students drink, smoke, dress in sexually provocative ways, fight, riot, injure one another, stay away from school and manifest other forms of maladaptive behaviours. These more often than not culminates into mass academic failure, drop out syndrome, cultism, rapism, unwanted and unintended pregnancy, mental delirium, dearth and untimely death.

School based interventions such as flogging, scolding and suspension geared towards checkmating maladaptive behaviours among the student population as observed by the researcher do not seem to yield the desired result given the persistence of the problem in view. More worrisome is the fact that they tend to aggravate the situation by predisposing the students to avoidant behaviour, substance abuse and self-harm. This tragic triad as envisaged by the researcher can culminate into deleterious and disastrous consequences such as psychological deterioration, impaired relationship, physical health risk, mental instability and allied suicidality. Hence the need to psychologically delve into the family relationship patterns of the students for solution or answers pertaining to the correlates of maladaptive behaviours among them. The researcher suspects that prevalent family relationship patterns such as; authoritarian parenting, neglectful parenting and parental conflict may be linked to maladaptive behaviour of students in Rivers State given that they have bearing on the self-concept, mental health, motivation, composure and exposure of the students as well as their vulnerability to negative pressure towards deviant or dysfunctional behaviour.

To the best of the researcher's knowledge and experience, little or no studies have been conducted on family relationship patterns as correlates of maladaptive behaviour of public senior secondary school students in Rivers State. And this has left well-meaning individuals and institutions concerned about how to stem the tide of maladaptive behaviour in the State in the dark as regards how these variables are related and the best course of remediative action. Therefore, the need arises to properly investigate family relationship patterns as correlates of maladaptive behaviour of public senior secondary school students in Rivers State.

Purpose of the Study

The aim of the study was to investigate family relationship patterns as correlates of maladaptive behaviour of public senior secondary school students in Rivers State. Specifically, the study sought to:

1. ascertain the relationship between authoritarian parenting as family pattern as correlates of maladaptive behaviour of public senior secondary school students in Rivers State;
2. determine the relationship between neglectful parenting as family pattern as correlates of maladaptive behaviour of public senior secondary school students in Rivers State;
3. find out the relationship between parental conflict as family pattern as correlates of maladaptive behaviour of public senior secondary school students in Rivers State;

Research Questions

The following research questions were answered in the study:

1. What is the relationship between authoritarian parenting as family pattern as correlates of maladaptive behaviour of public senior secondary school students in Rivers State?
2. What is the relationship between neglectful parenting as family pattern as correlates of maladaptive behaviour of public senior secondary school students in Rivers State?
3. What is the relationship between parental conflict as family pattern as correlates of maladaptive behaviour of public senior secondary school students in Rivers State?

Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses guided the study:

1. Authoritarian parenting as family pattern does not significantly relate to maladaptive behaviour of public senior secondary school students in Rivers State.
2. Neglectful parenting as family pattern does not significantly relate to maladaptive behaviour of public senior secondary school students in Rivers State.
3. Parental conflict as family pattern does not significantly relate to maladaptive behaviour of public senior secondary school students in Rivers State.

METHODOLOGY

The study adopted a correlational research design. The area of the study was Rivers State. The population of the study comprised the entire public senior secondary school two (SS2) students in Rivers State numbering 10,120 (Rivers State Post Primary Schools Board, 2025). The least tolerable sample size for the study as determined from the population using Taro Yamane formulae is 385. However, the sample was increased to 417 for better representation of the population. A sample size of 417 public senior secondary school students was therefore drawn from the population using the simple random sampling technique. The instrument for data collection was a researcher developed instrument titled: "Family Relationship Patterns and Maladaptive Behaviour Scale" (FSRPMBS). The face and content validities of the instrument were determined by two experts in Guidance and Counselling Department of Rivers State University, Port Harcourt. The reliability coefficients of the instrument were determined through the internal consistency method which yielded alpha coefficients of $\alpha=.87$ for (FSRPS) and $\alpha=.70$ for (MBS) deemed high enough to guarantee the use of the instrument for the study. The research questions and hypotheses were answered and tested using Pearson's product moment correlation statistics. All data were subjected to analysis using the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Research Question 1: *What is the relationship between authoritarian parenting as family pattern and maladaptive behaviour of public senior secondary school students in Rivers State?*

Hypothesis 1: Authoritarian parenting as family pattern does not significantly relate to maladaptive behaviour of public senior secondary school students in Rivers State.

Table 1: Pearson's Product Moment Correlation Analysis of the Relationship between Authoritarian Parenting and Maladaptive Behaviour

		Correlations	
		Authoritarian Parenting	Maladaptive Behaviour
Authoritarian Parenting	Pearson Correlation	1	.331**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	400	400
Maladaptive Behaviour	Pearson Correlation	.331*	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	400	400

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

Table 1 revealed that the calculated r was 0.331. This is a clear indicator that the result of this study is weak relations. That being, the relationship between authoritarian parenting and student maladaptive behaviour is weak (r=0.331). Therefore, the researcher concludes that authoritarian parenting as a family pattern had weak relationship between students' maladaptive behaviour. In other words, with authoritarian parenting, maladaptive behaviour is slightly increased.

For the testing of the hypothesis, the result of hypothesis 1 as indicated in Table 1 shows a significant relationship between authoritarian parenting as family pattern and maladaptive behaviour of public senior secondary school students in Rivers State as the calculated r=0.331 at the p-value of .000 of .05 level of significance. Thus, the null hypothesis earlier stated that authoritarian parenting as family pattern does not significantly relate to maladaptive behaviour of public senior secondary school students in Rivers State is rejected and the alternate hypothesis accepted that simply means, there is a significant relationship between authoritarian parenting and maladaptive behaviour of public senior secondary school students in Rivers State.

Research Question 2: *What is the relationship between neglectful parenting as family pattern and maladaptive behaviour of public senior secondary school students in Rivers State?*

Hypothesis 2: Neglectful parenting as family pattern does not significantly relate to maladaptive behaviour of public senior secondary school students in Rivers State.

Table 2: Pearson's Product Moment Correlation Analysis of the Relationship between Neglectful Parenting and Maladaptive Behaviour

		Correlations	
		Neglectful Parenting	Maladaptive Behaviour
Neglectful Parenting	Pearson Correlation	1	.706**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.001
	N	400	400
Maladaptive Behaviour	Pearson Correlation	.706**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.001	
	N	400	400

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

Table 2 revealed that the calculated r was 0.706. This is a clear indicator that the result of this study is strong relations. That being so, the relationship between neglectful parenting and student maladaptive behaviour is strong ($r=0.706$). Therefore, the researcher concludes that neglectful parenting as a family pattern had strong relationship between students' maladaptive behaviour. In other words, with neglectful parenting, maladaptive behaviour is highly increased.

For the testing of the hypothesis, the result of hypothesis 2 as indicated in Table 2 shows a significant relationship between neglectful parenting as family pattern and maladaptive behaviour of public senior secondary school students in Rivers State as the calculated $r=0.706$ at the p-value of .001 of .05 level of significance. Thus, the null hypothesis earlier stated that neglectful parenting as family pattern does not significantly relate to maladaptive behaviour of public senior secondary school students in Rivers State is rejected and the alternate hypothesis accepted that simply means, there is a significant relationship between neglectful parenting and maladaptive behaviour of public senior secondary school students in Rivers State.

Research Question 3: *What is the relationship between parental conflict as family pattern and maladaptive behaviour of public senior secondary school students in Rivers State?*

Hypothesis 3: Parental conflict as family pattern does not significantly relate to maladaptive behaviour of public senior secondary school students in Rivers State.

Table 3: Pearson's Product Moment Correlation Analysis of the Relationship between Parental Conflict and Maladaptive Behaviour

		Correlations	
		Parental Conflict	Maladaptive Behaviour
Parental Conflict	Pearson Correlation	1	.832**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	400	400
Maladaptive Behaviour	Pearson Correlation	.832**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	400	400

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

Table 3 revealed that the calculated r was 0.832. This is a clear indicator that the result of this study is strong relations. That being so, the relationship between parental conflict and student maladaptive behaviour is strong ($r=0.832$). Therefore, the researcher concludes that parental conflict as a family pattern had strong relationship between students' maladaptive behaviour. In other words, with parental conflict, maladaptive behaviour is highly increased.

For the testing of the hypothesis, the result of hypothesis 3 as indicated in Table 3 shows a significant relationship between parental conflict as family pattern and maladaptive behaviour of public senior secondary school students in Rivers State as the calculated $r=0.832$ at the p-value of .000 of .05 level of significance. Thus, the null hypothesis earlier stated that parental conflict as family pattern does not significantly relate to maladaptive behaviour of public senior secondary school students in Rivers State is rejected and the alternate hypothesis accepted that simply means, there is a significant relationship between parental conflict and maladaptive behaviour of public senior secondary school students in Rivers State.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

Authoritarian Parenting and Maladaptive Behaviour

The results of research question one and hypothesis one revealed that authoritarian parenting has a weak positive relationship ($r = .331$) with maladaptive behaviour of public senior secondary school students in Rivers State. This shows that parents that are authoritarian in nature try to inhibit maladaptive behaviour among their children considerably but they do not obliterate such behaviour entirely probably because

children raised using this parenting style harness any little opportunity at their disposal to try out things they are prohibited from doing. The result gives credence to the findings of Luyckx et al. (2011) which revealed among other things that authoritarian parenting style was significantly linked to maladaptive behaviour. These findings underscore the long-term influence of parenting practices on child behavior and highlight the critical need for early intervention and parent-focused education to foster healthier developmental pathways. The result equally consolidates the findings of Emami et al. (2024) which revealed that individuals with personality disorders scored significantly higher across all EMS domains and were more likely to report insecure attachment patterns and authoritarian parenting styles. This shows that authoritarian parenting is instrumental to the emergence of maladaptive behaviour. It works hand in hand with insecure attachment given the gap in affection and attention that characterize such parenting style. The statistical model effectively distinguished between clinical and non-clinical participants, with schemas related to disconnection, impaired autonomy, and attachment security emerging as particularly salient discriminators. These results suggest that interventions aimed at modifying maladaptive cognitive frameworks and early relational experiences may be effective in mitigating the onset or severity of personality disorders.

Neglectful Parenting and Maladaptive Behaviour

The results of research question two and hypothesis two revealed that neglectful parenting has a significant strong positive relationship ($r = .706$) with maladaptive behaviour of public senior secondary school students in Rivers State. What this means is that neglectful parenting is associated with a high increase in maladaptive behaviour among the students. The high positive relationship between neglectful parenting and maladaptive behaviour could be associated with needs deprivation and possible abandonment. The maladaptive behaviour exhibited by neglected children could therefore be an act of rebellion or a way of drawing attention to themselves and this is a serious matter. The result concatenates with the finding of Bedu-Addo et al. (2023) which revealed among other things that both physical and emotional neglect significantly predicted higher levels of malevolent creativity, specifically in behaviors such as deceitfulness, manipulation, and intent to harm others. The researchers concluded that neglectful and inconsistent parenting could contribute to the development of socially detrimental behaviors, urging communities to implement preventive strategies aimed at fostering healthier family dynamics and mitigating maladaptive personality development. The result supports the findings of Berzenski et al. (2013) which revealed that childhood neglect was a strong predictor of internalizing symptoms such as anxiety and withdrawal, and to a lesser degree, externalizing behaviors like aggression. Notably, parental distress was found to moderate the relationship between neglect and internalizing problems, indicating that children of distressed parents were more susceptible to internal psychological difficulties following neglect.

Parental Conflict and Maladaptive Behaviour

The results of research question three and hypothesis three revealed that parental conflict has a significant strong positive relationship ($r = .832$) with maladaptive behaviour of public senior secondary school students in Rivers State. This means that parental conflict is associated with a high increase in maladaptive behaviour among the students. It appears that parental conflict spills over into the affairs of their children by making them vulnerable to maladaptive behaviour. This could be attributed to transfer of aggression, exposure to unhealthy conflictual behaviour and allied stressors. The result confirms the findings of Saijad et al. (2017) that repeated exposure to parental discord can disrupt a child's psychological stability and social behavior, leading to internalized emotional struggles such as distress, anxiety, or social withdrawal. The result equally gives credence to the findings of Kong et al. (2024) which revealed among other things that parental conflict was found to have a negative correlation with family functioning and a positive correlation with shyness and loneliness. Notably, family functioning partially mediated the relationship between parental conflict and shyness, and fully mediated the link between parental conflict and loneliness. The results suggest that a well-functioning family environment can buffer the harmful emotional outcomes of parental conflict, with a particularly strong protective effect

against adolescent loneliness. This highlights the central role of family cohesion and adaptability in safeguarding youth emotional well-being.

CONCLUSION

The findings of this study indicate that family relationship patterns play a crucial role in shaping the behavioural outcomes of public secondary school students in Rivers State. Specifically, neglectful parenting and parental conflict were found to have a strong and significant positive relationship with maladaptive behaviour, suggesting that students exposed to these conditions are more likely to develop problematic behaviours. Additionally, although authoritarian parenting also showed a significant relationship with maladaptive behaviour, its influence was comparatively weaker. Overall, these results underscore the importance of fostering supportive, stable, and nurturing home environments to promote positive behavioural development among students.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings of the study, the researcher recommended as follows:

1. Authoritarian parents should adopt a more supportive and communicative approach by explaining the reasons behind family rules; this can help reduce maladaptive behaviour and promote adolescents' emotional and social development, in line with the goals of Sustainable Development Goal 4, which advocates supportive environments for quality education and positive youth development.
2. Neglectful parents should strive to take good care of their children by meeting their needs, listening to them and monitoring their behaviours to curtail maladaptive behaviour.
3. Parents should strive to live in peace by harnessing conflict resolution strategies such as negotiation, mediation, conciliation and accommodation to resolve their conflicts amicably and by so doing mitigate maladaptive behaviour.

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